

URBAN-WASTE – 690452 – D8.4

URBAN-WASTE

Urban strategies for Waste Management in Tourist Cities

D8.4 - Newsletter

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Abstract

This deliverable reports on the 6 newsletters that were sent out over the project's lifetime as an essential part of the communication and dissemination activities. This deliverable summarises their structure, content and outreach.

Contributors

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List of abbreviations

ACR+	Association of Cities and Regions for Recycling and Sustainable Resource management
CE	Consulta Europa
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Structure.....	4
2.1 <i>Structure.....</i>	4
2.2 <i>Dissemination of the newsletter</i>	5
3. Measuring Impact: Data and Figures	6
3.1 <i>Contacts and Audience.....</i>	6
3.2 <i>Impact: figures and trends.....</i>	6
ANNEX I: HTML VERSIONS OF THE NEWSLETTERS	8

1. Introduction

The Newsletter was already defined as one of the key dissemination channel of the project, namely because it would include people who explicitly agreed to subscribe to it. This fact would ensure that the information the project disseminates reaches the appropriate target group.

The URBAN-WASTE Newsletter was a valuable and efficient tool of dissemination, informing the external readers about the general development of the project, as well as an important mean to stimulate stakeholders' engagement. It served to regularly spread not only news and updates about the project itself, but also concerning all the relevant initiatives and measures taken by the project's 11 pilot cities and regions, directly involving them in the dissemination process. Moreover, URBAN-WASTE Newsletter was used to divulgate the project's public deliverables and to increase their relevance among the European stakeholders.

Newsletters were sent out every six months, with a total of six releases. Readability was paid a special attention to concerning both the content and the graphic representation: its layout has been developed according to the project's visual identity and the article were kept short, offering the readers all the links to the original articles or publications, as they were all published on the website.

2. Structure

2.1 Structure

The URBAN-WASTE Newsletter's structure was made up of four main sections.

'Project News' featured four articles including updates, achievements and milestones of the project, as well as presenting new deliverables mainly written by ACR+ or the responsible for a certain deliverable. 'News from pilot cities and regions' included six articles per newsletter provided by the pilots usually informing the readers about the launch and/or implementation of one of the eco-innovative measures in the pilots, but also other news related to general waste management or tourism in the 11 pilots

Following the first two sections dedicated to the project's development and news, two permanent links to the e-CoP and Municipality Forum are included in each of the newsletter, allowing readers to easily get updates about those. As those pages on the website were kept alive with updated content, this part presented an important contribution to the capacity building, especially providing knowledge acquired by URBAN-WASTE to external readers.

The third section 'Meet our cities and regions' featured two cities or regions per newsletter. Clicking on the icons, the reader was able to be re-directed to the URBAN-WASTE website to learn more about the pilot cities and regions of the project.

The fourth and last section, 'Latest Publications', included a variable number of brief introductory paragraphs presenting the reader the latest project's public deliverables, each of them followed by the link to the full publication.

Each of the articles included a related picture. The language used was English for all the six newsletters. The structure of the newsletter is presented visually in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Structure of the Newsletter

2.2 Dissemination of the newsletter

The URBAN-WASTE newsletters represent one of the major dissemination channels of the project. The newsletters were structured and built up as described in the paragraph 1.2. Before sending them out through a

mass-mailing software, the newsletter was being approved by the project coordinator through a test email for verifying each newsletter's quality and content.

Only the very first Newsletter was delayed 2 months, as the website wasn't set up yet, therefore it was not possible to create articles which would be later featured in the Newsletter.

The dissemination channels included:

- 📧 Mailing lists; as described in the following chapter
- 📧 Social media: the HTML versions of the newsletter were shared and circulated on Facebook and Twitter, through URBAN-WASTE official profiles
- 📧 The HTML versions of the newsletters were uploaded on the website, under the section '[News > Newsletter](#)'

3. Measuring Impact: Data and Figures

3.1 Contacts and Audience

Initial subscription to the newsletter happened prior to the first issue of it (November 2016) with the support of the project partners and their contact databases. Each partner provided ACR+ with at least 10 contacts agreed to be included in the newsletter dissemination list. Later on, potential readers were asked to subscribe in order to comply with privacy policies and GDPR. The initial dissemination list went through the same procedure. Potential recipients had the chance to choose whether to subscribe or not.

The dissemination list was composed of contacts and their emails acquired through:

- 📧 Website – the website had a permanent "Sign Up" form which added them to the dissemination list
- 📧 Capacity building activities – events such as webinars or Mutual Learnings or other events which required an online registration contained a question whether the registrant wanted to receive newsletters; the contacts were then added manually to the dissemination list
- 📧 Other physical events – physical events like fairs, info days, participation in conferences, congresses, but also open-air events organised by the project partners contained a simple printed blank contact list which was offered to participants and visitors to add their name to and later be added to the dissemination list

3.2 Impact: figures and trends

The regular analysis of the newsletter impact was based on three main indicators: number of people reached (audience); number of mail openings; number of clicks.

The first sending reached a total of 621 recipients, while the sixth and last one reached 753 people, showing a linear growth in the audience. For the other two indicators, there is no linear trend: impact varied throughout the months, swinging between ups and downs. Considering the mail openings¹, the number was not following the number of recipients, and the share of subscribers who actually opened the Newsletters fell from 32% (for

¹ The number of mails actually being opened and read instead of deleted or redirected to spam

the first two Newsletters) to around 23% (for the other 4). The last Newsletter was sent out only few days prior to this deliverable and therefore the outreach analysis is not very reliable.

Concerning clicks², the general trend is also negative, but not linear nor stable. It also fell from 28% of interaction among those who opened the email to 23.4%. These figures are better presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The statistical analysis of the URBAN-WASTE Newsletters' outreach

² Clicks represent the interaction with the newsletter and imply the number of articles read on the website by clicking on "read more"

ANNEX I: HTML VERSIONS OF THE NEWSLETTERS

[Newsletter #1; February 2017](#)

[Newsletter #2; May 2017](#)

[Newsletter #3; November 2018](#)

[Newsletter #4; May 2019](#)

[Newsletter #5; November 2019](#)

[Newsletter #6; May 2019](#)

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